

A COMPARATIVE CLINICAL STUDY OF HOMOEOPATHIC MEDICINES NATRUM MURIATICUM AND IGNATIA IN CASES OF PERSISTENT COMPLEX BEREAVEMENT DISORDER IN AGE GROUP OF 18 TO 60 YEARS

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ABSTRACT

AIM : The goal of this study is to evaluate the efficacy of homoeopathic medications, Natrum muriaticum and Ignatia Amara in the treatment of Persistent Complex Bereavement Disorder. (also known as Prolonged Grief Disorder). Along with addressing the need for more research into prevention, early intervention, and treatment modalities, it also aims to evaluate symptom relief and the effect on comorbid conditions. **METHOD :** A non-randomized, Single blind clinical study was conducted at the Bharati Vidyapeeth (Deemed to be University) Homoeopathic Medical College & Research Centre, Pune. 32 patients male and female (age 18-60 years) diagnosed with PGD, based on ICD-11 and DSM-V criteria were enrolled, out of which 2 dropped out and 30 patients completed their 5 follow ups. A PGD questionnaire was used to calculate the PGD score. Depending on symptom similarity, patients were prescribed Ignatia Amara or Natrum muriaticum. **RESULT :** There was a significant decline in PGD scores. Before therapy, the mean PGD score was 14.73 ± 3.92 ; after treatment, it was 6.10 ± 2.90 ($p < 0.05$). Patients reported great symptomatic reduction with no side effects from both medications, which were effective in reducing PGD symptoms. **CONCLUSION :** Ignatia Amara and Natrum muriaticum act effectively for treating Persistent Complex Bereavement Disorder. Further to better understand the pathophysiology and develop more potent treatment alternatives, this study emphasizes the necessity for additional research with a bigger sample size and control group.

KEYWORDS : Persistent complex bereavement disorder, prolonged grief disorder, single blind study, Homoeopathy.

INTRODUCTION :

Grief is a natural response to the loss of a loved one, material possessions, or intangible aspects like self-esteem. While grief is generally a temporary process, shock may initially occur, causing feelings of confusion, numbness, or denial. This shock can last from hours to weeks, depending on the significance of the loss and other factors. As grief progresses, emotional and physical symptoms like crying, difficulty breathing, weakness, and trouble concentrating emerge. These symptoms typically last 4-6 weeks but may extend up to six months. Uncomplicated grief resolves over time and usually doesn't require psychiatric treatment. ⁽¹⁾

DEFINITION :

According to the new Oxford textbook of psychiatry; bereavement refers to the complex set of reactions that occurs following the death of a loved one, including the emotions of grief with yearning, angry protest, and sadness; the cognitive processes of understanding and making meaning of the finality and nature of death; and the social, cultural, spiritual, and religious contexts of adjustment. Grief may also be caused by other losses such as health, home, country, and safe worlds. ⁽²⁾

PREVALENCE :

Persistent complex bereavement disorder has prevalence of approximately of 2.4% - 4.8%. This disorder is more prevalent in women than men. ⁽³⁾

PHENOMOLOGY OF NORMAL GRIEF :

Research shows that adults commonly experience grief through disbelief, anger, numbness, yearning, and sadness, gradually leading to acceptance. According to Bonanno's studies, many people show

resilience with low distress levels. Brief symptoms, such as feeling the deceased's presence, are also observed. Yearning, the most characteristic feature, usually diminishes within a year but can be triggered by memories or anniversaries. Elderly people may find comfort in talking to a deceased spouse. Grief typically peaks in disbelief, yearning, anger, and sadness. While intense grief lessens within 4-6 months, prolonged grief may indicate a pathological response, especially in vulnerable individuals.⁽²⁾

NEUROBIOLOGY OF BEREAVEMENT :

Recent studies have investigated the neurobiology of bereavement making use of functional magnetic resonance imaging and brain activity in women grieving over the end of romantic relationship. Researchers attempted to build a theoretical model based on a wide range of relevant data, including a 'neuro-bio-psychosocial' framework for sorrow and loss.⁽²⁾

The article "Regional Brain Activity in Women Grieving a Romantic Relationship Breakup" explores how breakups impact brain activity in women using fMRI. Key findings include:

1. **Increased Activity in Reward and Attachment Areas:** Breakups trigger heightened brain activity in regions linked to reward, attachment, and social pain.
2. **Similarity to Physical Pain:** Emotional pain from breakups activates brain areas similarly to physical pain.
3. **Cognitive Impact:** Breakups affect cognitive functions such as working memory and rumination.
4. **Study Methodology:** Participants viewed images of ex-partners and performed memory tasks, revealing changes in brain activity.
5. **Therapeutic Implications:** Understanding these brain patterns can inform treatments for breakup-related emotional pain.

The study highlights that emotional and physical pain share common neural pathways.⁽²⁾

CLASSIFICATION OF GRIEF :

Fig 1-Explaining classification of grief Grief's reaction has been classified into normal grief and morbid grief.

Further morbid grief has been divided into pathological and complicated grief reaction.

PATHOLOGICAL GRIEF REACTION - When one or more of the symptoms of normal grief are magnified or when the duration exceeds 6 months without natural recovery, grief becomes pathological. Pathological grief is further classified into various subtypes.

COMPLICATED GRIEF REACTION - In this, the grief is complicated by neurotic or psychotic illness, along with the symptoms of grief. It includes various subtypes as hysterical, obsessive-compulsive, phobia, sudden psychotic episodes or mania. ⁽¹⁾

DIAGNOSTIC FEATURES : ⁽³⁾

For adults, it no less than six of the following symptoms appear more frequently than not and persist for 12 months after a loss, they may suggest persistent complex bereavement.

1. Struggle to accept the loss.
2. Feelings of disbelief or emotional numbness over loss.
3. Finding it difficult to remember the lost one positively.
4. Bitterness or resentment over the loss.
5. Negative self-views or self-blame related to the death.
6. Avoiding reminders of the loss (places, people, situations, or in children , feelings and thoughts).
7. Desire to die to be with the deceased.
8. Finding it difficult to trust others after the loss.
9. Feeling isolated or detached from others.
10. Feeling unable to function or seeing life as meaningless without the deceased.
11. Confusion regarding one's role or identity.
12. Difficulty in pursuing new interests or planning for future.

DIFFERENTIAL DIAGNOSIS:

Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD), also known as Persistent Complex Bereavement Disorder (PCBD), is distinct from normal grief due to its intense grief reactions lasting over twelve months. It is diagnosed when these reactions interfere with daily functioning. PGD differs from depressive disorders, such as major depressive disorder and persistent depressive disorder, which focus on sadness, crying, and suicidal thoughts, while PGD centres on loss. PGD can also co-occur with Post-traumatic Stress-Disorder (PTSD), where both share avoidance and intrusive thoughts. However, PGD intrusions focus on the relationship with the deceased, while PTSD revolves around the traumatic event. Additionally, PGD involves distress tied to separation, unlike Separation Anxiety Disorder, which focuses on anxiety from detachment from living individuals. Grief after a traumatic death may lead to both PGD and PTSD, with symptoms like distressing death-related delusions and obsession over the loss in PGD. ⁽³⁾

TREATMENT/MANAGEMENT :

Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD), also known as Persistent Complex Bereavement Disorder (PCBD), is a condition marked by intense and prolonged grief reactions that last more than twelve months and interfere with daily life. It differs from normal grief by its duration and severity. PGD is distinct from depressive disorders like major depressive disorder and persistent depressive disorder, which emphasize sadness, crying, and suicidal thoughts, while PGD primarily focuses on the loss of the loved one. PGD may co-occur with Post-traumatic Stress- Disorder (PTSD), as both conditions involve avoidance and intrusive thoughts. However, PGD intrusions center on the relationship with the deceased, whereas PTSD is focused on the traumatic event itself. In PGD, distress stems from separation, unlike in Separation Anxiety Disorder, which involves anxiety tied to detachment from living individuals. Traumatic grief, following a tragic death, can result in PGD and PTSD symptoms, including distressing death-related delusions and an obsessive yearning for the departed, further complicating the grieving process. ⁽⁴⁾

HOMOEOPATHIC REMEDIES :

Natrum muriaticum and Ignatia Amara are the remedies that every homeopath thinks of first when considering the treatment of deep or prolonged grief reactions.

1. NATRUM MURIATICUM :

Common name – common salt
Chemical formula – NaCl
source – Mineral kingdom

Preparation – chemical preparation- trituration and aqueous solution

INDICATIONS OF NATRUM MURIATICUM

Natrum muriaticum is a deep acting remedy, it makes long lasting effects when given in apotentized doses.

Table 1- indications of natrum muriaticum given in various homoeopathy books

Sr.no.	Name of homoeopathic materia medica	Natrum muriaticum symptoms in grief
1.	Lectures on homoeopathy by Kent J.T.	Natrum is highly sensitive to emotions, quickly absorbing anguish and despair, often for no apparent reason. Her mood alternates between sobbing and smiling, followed by deep despair. Despite her joyful surroundings, she struggles to be happy and frequently reflects on previous hurts. Does not like consolation and has headaches as a result of her depression, which is frequently caused by unrequited affection.[5]
2.	Materia medica by Boericke W.	Ill effects of grief, psychic causes of disease, anger, fright etc. depressed in chronic diseases , aggravation by consolation. Irritable, hasty , awkward, wants to be alone to cry. Laughter with tears. Suppressed menses, irregular. Emaciation present. Headache with pale face, nausea, vomiting, periodical, menstruation. [6]
3.	Keynotes with nosodes by Allen H.C.	Great emaciation, irritability, cries from slightest cause, disposition to weep , sad mood without any cause but consolation aggravates. drops things due to nervous weakness, headache with blindness. [7]
4.	Homoeopathic drug pictures by M.L. Tyler.	Mentally is irritable, hates consolation , broods over old disagreeable- old insults and becomes miserable over it. Weeps more, falls in love with wrong person and breaks her heart, hates company. [8]
5.	Condensed materia medica by Hering C	Struggles with concentration, often absent-minded and forgetful, with clumsy speech and a distant demeanour. Sadness leads to tears, but comfort only angers her, causing a racing heart. Worries constantly, dwells on past problems, and feels drained by life. Indifferent and joyless, she retreats inward with deep sorrow, even in matters of faith. There’s a lasting sense of emptiness, little appetite, and a craving for salty or bitter foods.[9]
6.	Homoeopathic Psychology by Philip bailey	Natrum mur patients are extremely sensitive to loss, frequently responding with numbness or extended mourning. They either shut down emotionally or feel extreme, long-term grief, sobbing profusely. These peoplehide their feelings because they want to be strong for their family or prevent depression. Loss affects them severely, whether through death or separation.[10]

7.	Essence of materia medica by George Vithoukas	Natrum patients are emotionally sensitive, predisposed to grief, and introverted. They hardly express their feelings freely and prefer isolation to reflect on their grief. Grief causes excessive crying and bodily trembling, and they hate consoling. They frequently seek out the saddest music, intensifying their grief rather than expressing it. ⁽¹¹⁾
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Relationship of natrum muriaticum :

- Complementary – Ignatia ; Apis ; sepia ⁽¹³⁾
- Antidotes – arsenic album, camphora, phosphorous, nux vomica, sepia ⁽¹³⁾
- Prescription - twelfth to thirtieth or higher potency. The higher potencies yield best results.^[6]

2. IGNATIA AMARA Common name – St Ignatius Bean
Source - vegetable kingdom
Family – Loganiaceae

Preparation – seeds of the tree used to prepare mother tincture. ⁽⁴⁾

INDICATIONS OF IGNATIA AMARA

This remedy is frequently used and is specifically suited to sensitive, delicate women and children.⁽⁵⁾

Table 2 - indications of Ignatia given in various homoeopathy books

Sr. no.	Name of homoeopathic materia medica	Ignatia symptoms in grief
1.	Lectures on homoeopathy by Kent J.T.	Suffers from grief, has been disturbed, excited and goes into cramps, headache, trembles and quivers. Weeping spells, headache, sleepless, nervous after disappointed love, after losing her husband, child. Unable to control herself despite best efforts but her grief torn her to pieces. Not able to control her emotions. Weakness of the body, hysterical and fainting fits. (5)
2.	Materia medica by Boericke W.	There is rapid change in mental and physical conditions. Emotional element is more marked and coordination with function is interfered. Chief remedy for hysteria, suited to sensitive, easily excited, mild disposition person. Effects of grief, shock, disappointment and worry. There is changeable mood, broods silently, sad, tearful, melancholic, does not communicate, sobbing and sighing. Feeling of lump in the throat, menses suppression from grief. Grief causes insomnia (6)
3.	Keynotes with nosodes by Allen H.C.	Suitable for anxious, sensitive ladies who are quickly stimulated or affected by wrath, sadness, or negative news. Grief produces spasmodic laughing, characterized by abrupt changes in mood from joy to sorrow, laughter to tears. Long-term grief drains people psychologically and physically. They obsess over imagined problems, crave seclusion, and are agitated by little feelings.(7)
4.	Homoeopathic drug pictures by M.L. Tyler.	Mental stress caused by shock, sadness, or disappointment might manifest as crying and obsessing over previous events. It produces intense sadness, insomnia, and despondency. The patient has mood swings, anxiety, and hysteric outbursts. Chorea, which is characterized by twitching throughout the body, is particularly useful for grief-related instances.(8)

5.	Condensed materia medica by Hering C	Ailments from bad news, grief, there is great grief after losing persons or objects that were very dear. Anger is followed by silent grief or sorrow. Desire to be alone, absent-minded, changeable mood; joyfulness and laughing changes to sadness and shedding tears. Effects of disappointed love. (9)
.	Homoeopathic Psychology by Philipbailey	Ignatia is the go-to remedy for prolonged grief. Bereavement causes excessive crying, emotional instability, and mood swings between wrath and mute sadness. Physical symptoms include nausea, a lump in the throat, lack of appetite, and hysteria, which can result in muscular spasms or paralysis. It suits any constitution following sadness. (10)
7.	Materia medica pura 2 by Hahnemann.	Ignatia is given in consequences from deep-seated emotions, particularly grief. There is sadness and fixed insanity caused by grief, fear, suffering, weeping. Amenorrhoea from suppressed grief. Congestive toothache due to grief. Dwells upon grief. (12)

Relationship of Ignatia Amara :

- Complementary - natrum muriaticum⁽¹³⁾
- Inimical – Coffea, nux vomica, tabacum⁽¹³⁾
- Antidotes – arnica , Coffea, pulsatilla, nux vomica , cocculus⁽¹³⁾
- Prescription – sixth to 200th potency. Usually best administered in the morning. (2)

To treat persistent complex bereavement disorder (PGD), homeopathy offers a safe, cost- effective option. Remedies like Natrum muriaticum and Ignatia Amara are effective in addressing grief-related symptoms. By matching remedies to individual symptoms, patients can find relief from prolonged grief without new issues. These remedies have been successfully used in homeopathy for many years.

OBJECTIVES

Prolonged Grief Disorder is a recently recognised mental health disorder and patients mostly rely on anti-depressants, anti-anxiety, sedatives etc. Homoeopathy effectively treats grief disorder and its symptoms with no side effects and is cost effective. The objective of the present clinical study is to study homeopathic medicines efficacy in managing grief disorder reducing its symptoms recurrency and enhancing quality of life in patients.

MATERIAL & METHOD

This non-randomized single blind clinical study based on the data relating to the Prolonged grief disorder treatment with homoeopathic remedies Natrum Muriaticum and Ignatia Amara carried out with detailed case studies and their follow up on patient aged between 18 to 60 years age in the Out Patient Department. The study was carried out as a part of a Post- Graduate Research Project and all the possible relevant details of the patients were collected and recorded in the case papers. The above observed data after a detailed assessment were analysed and appropriate statistical significance tests were applied and the results are presented in this paper.

CTRI registration number - CTRI/2023/02/049583

Case definition :

Patients within the age group of 18 to 60 years with complaint of grief for more than 6 months were considered for the study. Patients qualifying the guidelines given by Diagnostic and statistical manual of Mental disorders 5th edition (DSM-V).

Inclusion Criteria :

- Patients fulfilling the DSM-V diagnostic criteria and questionnaire criteria
- Patients of both sexes.
- Patients ranging from age 18-60 yrs and of various socio-economic groups were included.

- Patients without other systemic diseases.
- Patient giving written consent form.
- Patients qualifying the said set of symptom similarity of the remedies (Natrum Muriaticum , Ignatia)

Exclusion criteria :

- Cases which do not fulfil DSM-V diagnostic criteria and questionnaire criteria
- Cases with serious complication of PGD
- Pregnant and lactating women
- Cases associated with systemic disorders were excluded
- Patients who have taken part in any other research study over the past six months.

Selection of Remedy :

30 patients with PGD of both sexes and age group 18 to 60 years were enrolled in this study. Case taking was done according to homoeopathic principles, and the medicines were given as per the indication based on totality of symptoms. In cases where medicine was not necessary, only placebo was prescribed, in the form of sugar of milk globules.

Selection of Potency :

Potency selection was done according to the Posology rules as per 6th edition of organon of medicine.

Storage of Drugs :

Drugs were stored in Bharati Vidyapeeth Homeopathic Hospital pharmacy, Katraj, Pune as per the rules of pharmacopeia (HPI), under appropriate temperature, Log no. & batch no. was maintained.

Follow up :

- Each case was followed up for approximately three months .
- All the patients were followed up on properly, and details of clinical & symptomatic changes were recorded .
- Follow-up varies from patient to patient.

Assessment Criteria :

Marked improvement	When the prolonged grief disorder score has been reduced by more than 75%
Moderate improvement	When the prolonged grief disorderscore is reduced between 50% - 75%
Mild improvement	When the prolonged grief disorderscore is reduced less than 50 %

Table 3 - assessment criteria

Parameters used in assessment :

Persistent complex bereavement disorder questionnaire used.

Persistent complex bereavement disorder questionnaire was prepared. This questionnaire consists of 10 questions based on reactions after grief and four response categories. The answers to the questions are added up to produce a total numerical score. The sub scores range from 0 to 3 (least significant – 0 and most significant – 3), with a total score ranging from 0-30.

Outcome Assessment :

The outcome was measured after completion of five follow-ups. Improvement of patients was assessed by the difference between the total number of scorings of questionnaire before and after the treatment. Starting and ending scores were computed & compared to see whether there is improvement or not. All outcome data was examined using statistical tests to determine the efficacy or otherwise of the treatment , student paired ‘t’ test was applied to carry out the statistical analysis. The statistical analysis aided in determining whether the differences seen before and after

interventions were significant or not.

Results :

This study includes 30 cases in the age group of 18-60 years as sample (n=30), who has been diagnosed with Prolonged Grief Disorder . All these 30 cases were followed up on for a period of 3 months. Data from these 30 cases were gathered and statistically analyzed. In this section, tables and charts are used to describe the information from 30 cases. The highest percentage of patients belonged to the age group of 18-22 years (53.33%) and lowest from the age group of 27-32 years. 12 participants were male (40 %) and 18 were female (60%). 15 (50%) patients were given natrum muriaticum and 15(50%) were given ignatia. Along with PGD symptoms out of 30 11 (36.67%) patients showed anxiety. Out of 30 patients

Demographic data given in Table below.

Table 4: Age wise distribution of the patients.

Age Group	Number of patients	Percentage
18-22	16	53.33%
22-27	8	26.67%
27-32	2	6.67%
Above 32	4	13.33%

Table 5: Gender distribution of patients

Gender	Number of Patients	Percentage
Female	18	60%
Male	12	40%

Table 6 : Medicine-wise distribution of patients.

Medicine	Number of patients	Percentage
Ignatia	15	50%
Natrum Mur	15	50%

Table 7 : Distribution of patient’s anxiety-wise.

Anxiety	Number of patients	Percentage
Absent	19	63.33%
Present	11	36.67%

Test for hypothesis

Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD) score difference is calculated as difference between PGD

score before and after the treatment.

Hypotheses tested:

Null Hypothesis Ho: There is no significant difference between the two medicines Ignatia Amara and Natrum Muriaticum as far as Average PGD score difference is concerned.

Against

Alternative Hypothesis H1: There is a significant difference between the two medicines Ignatia Amara and Natrum Muriaticum as far as Average PGD score difference is concerned. To test the hypothesis, the two-sample 't-test' was used.

Table 8 : Two sample 't- test' for Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD) score difference between two groups with medicines Ignatia Amara and Natrum Muriaticum.

Variable	Medicine	N	Mean difference ± Sd (ng/mL)	Test statistic	P-value
PGD score difference	Ignatia Amara	15	8.47± 2.70	T-stat with df 28=-0.33	P-value =0.74 ons
	Natrum Muriaticum	15	8.80± 2.76		
Estimate for difference:			-0.33	95% CI for difference	(2.37, 1.70)

Table 8 gives the descriptive statistics and two sample t-test of the Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD) score difference between two groups with medicines Ignatia Amara and Natrum Muriaticum.

Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD) score difference for Ignatia Amara was 8.47±2.70 (Mean±Sd). For Natrum Muriaticum, the Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD) score difference was 8.80±2.76.

The test statistic value with df 28 was -0.33.

Here, P Value 0.740 (>0.05) is statistically non-significant.

We reject Ho, concluding that, there is no substantial difference between the two medicines Ignatia Amara and Natrum Muriaticum as far as Average PGD score difference is concerned.

Hypotheses tested:

Ho: There is no significant difference between the Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD) score before and after treatment. (Homoeopathic medicines Natrum Muriaticum and Ignatia Amara are not effective in relieving prolonged grief disorder in patients.)

Alternative Hypothesis H1: There is a significant difference between Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD) score before and after treatment. (Homoeopathic medicines Natrum Muriaticum and Ignatia Amara are effective in relieving prolonged grief disorder in patients.)

For hypothesis testing paired 't-test' is applied.

Table 9 : Paired ‘t-test’ and Descriptive statistics of the PGD Score before and after the intervention.

PGD Score	N	Mean±SD	T Statistic Value	P-Value
Before intervention	30	14.73±3.92	17.62	0.000 **
after intervention	30	6.10 ±2.90		
95% CI For mean difference:	(7.63, 9.63)			

Table 9 descriptive Statistics and paired t-test results of the Prolonged Grief Disorder(PGD) score before and after the intervention. Before treatment, the Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD)score was 14.73 ± 3.92

(mean± SD) which reduced to 6.10 ± 2.90 after treatment.

To test the hypothesis of whether the average PGD score of patients, before and after the intervention of Homoeopathic medicine remains the same or not, the Paired t-test is used. T-statistic value is 17.62 with a p-value of 0.000 ** highly significant.

We reject Ho and conclude that There is a significant difference between the Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD) score before and after treatment. Homoeopathic medicines Natrum Muriaticum and Ignatia Amaraare effective in relieving prolonged grief disorder in patients.

Table 10 : Improvement-wise distribution of patients.

Improvement	Number of patients	Percentage
Marked	15	50.0%
Mild	3	10.0%
Moderate	10	33.3%
No improvement	2	6.7%

Table 10 show the distribution of patients according to improvement level. 50% of the patients had marked improvement in Prolonged Grief Disorder, 33% of patients had moderate improvement, 10% of patients had mild improvement and remaining 7% had no improvement in Prolonged Grief Disorder.

Discussion :

Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD), additionally referred to as persistent complex bereavement, influences 2.4% to 4.8% of bereaved adults. preliminary care of grieving people requires empathy, aid, and addressing immediate needs to shield mental fitness. complications like melancholy, PTSD, anxiety, insomnia, and substance use can also arise and are handled with medicinal drugs like antidepressants or sedatives, alongside bereavement counseling. whilst medications aren't recommended for grief itself, they will help with complications. Cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) and rehabilitation are also beneficial for PGD.

However, PGD is often overlooked, and more studies are required on treatment options and early intervention. This study aimed to determine if the homeopathic drugs Natrum Muriaticum and Ignatia Amara could help treat PGD. Thirty patients (18-60 years) from Bharati Vidyapeeth Homoeopathic Medical college in Pune participated. The diagnosis was primarily based on DSM-V criteria, and patients acquired either Natrum Muriaticum or Ignatia Amara for 3 months, with follow-ups every 15 days. signs and symptoms and PGD questionnaire scores were compared before and after intervention.

Out of 30 patients, 15 showed marked improvement, 10 showed moderate improvement and 5 showed little to no change. The PGD score significantly decreased, and no adverse side effects were reported. The study concluded that homeopathic treatment, combined with mindfulness and physical activity, can help alleviate PGD symptoms.

CONCLUSION :

The study suggests that Natrum Muriaticum and Ignatia Amara, two homeopathic remedies, are effective in treating Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD). Among 32 participants, 30 completed the trial. Using a paired "t" test, statistical analysis confirmed the benefit of these treatments in reducing PGD symptoms. The average PGD score significantly decreased from 14.73 ± 3.92 to 6.10 ± 2.90 after treatment. This indicates that symptom-based homeopathic prescriptions can help alleviate PGD. Despite promising results, the study's small sample size and short duration suggest that further research with larger groups and longer periods is needed to confirm the efficacy of these treatments for prolonged grief disorder.

SUMMARY :

Prolonged Grief Disorder (PGD), also called Persistent Complex Bereavement Disorder, is a newly recognized mental health condition that can deeply impact a person's life. Those with PGD experience overwhelming, long-lasting grief that disrupts their daily routines. Unfortunately, this condition is often overlooked, leading to further mental health issues like depression, anxiety, PTSD, insomnia, and even substance abuse. While medications like antidepressants are commonly used to treat these issues, they can sometimes lead to dependency. Other treatments, such as cognitive behavioral therapy (CBT) and rehabilitation, have been shown to help manage PGD.

A recent study at Bharati Vidyapeeth Homoeopathic Medical Hospital studied the efficacy of two homeopathic remedies—Natrum Muriaticum and Ignatia Amara to treat PGD. Participants, aged 18 to 60, diagnosed with PGD based on DSM-V criteria were enrolled in the study. Over a course of year, 30 people completed the study with regular 5 follow-ups.

The results showed significant improvement in PGD symptoms: 50% of patients experienced marked improvement, 33% moderate improvement, 10% mild improvement, and 7% saw no change.

Homeopathic treatment with Natrum Muriaticum and Ignatia Amara demonstrated efficacy in reducing PGD symptoms, with both remedies proving equally effective. The study concluded that

homeopathy offers a viable treatment option for Persistent Complex Bereavement Disorder.

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Statement Of Conflict of Interest

Authors declare there is no conflict of interest.

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